

IMPACT OF AEROACOUSTICS ON AERODYNAMIC DAMPING IN A TRANSONIC 1 1/2-STAGE AXIAL COMPRESSOR

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ABSTRACT

New developments in turbomachinery designs require longer and thinner blades, which are prone to high vibration amplitudes and flutter. Predicting aerodynamic damping and understanding its mechanisms, flutter in particular, have been a research topic for many years. However, most investigations have been purely based on numerical simulations. In this paper, the impact of aeroacoustic mode propagation on aerodynamic damping in a transonic 1 1/2-stage axial compressor is investigated. Harmonic balance calculations of the compressor are performed, sequentially adding parts of the compressor to the domain. The acoustic mode propagation is then investigated by means of a radial mode analysis. The numerically calculated aerodynamic damping is compared with experimentally obtained damping at that operating point by means of an acoustic excitation system. The results show that neighbouring vane rows can significantly influence the aerodynamic damping, especially, but not exclusively, when the acoustic modes are cut-on. The reflection behaviour of the neighbouring vane rows was also found to be dependent on the cut-on state of the scatter modes; even parts which are located further away from the rotor - as e.g. struts - can influence the aerodynamic damping due to acoustic reflections. However, in this work the extension of the computational domain mainly decreases non-physical reflections by the boundary conditions, leading to a more accurate prediction. Acoustic waves propagating through the blade passage experience phase jump at the shock, which can presumably lead to a completely different behaviour as at subsonic operating points.

Keywords: Aeroelasticity, Aerodynamic Damping, Compressor, Aeroacoustics

1 INTRODUCTION

Modern turbomachinery designs often feature longer and thinner blades, which are prone to high vibration amplitudes and flutter. The damping of blade vibrations is usually dominated by aerodynamic damping, especially when no large friction damping is present (e.g. blisks). Research on prediction methods for aerodynamic damping and its mechanisms, in particular flutter, has been ongoing for many years. However, most investigations have been performed on a purely numerical basis, as the measurement of aerodynamic damping during operation of compressors and turbines is very challenging. With improving computational resources and methods, more specifically frequency-domain methods, it was found that under many conditions the calculation of the isolated rotor is insufficient, as acoustic interactions with other blade rows and test rig components influence the aerodynamic damping. There are two main aeroacoustic mechanisms that impact the aerodynamic damping:

1. Acoustic propagation
2. Cut-on/cut-off conditions

Acoustic propagation. Many earlier papers are focused on fan-intake coupling, where blade vibrations excite acoustic modes which travel upstream, are reflected at the intake lip, and hit the blades with a different phase angle. Depending on intake-lip reflection behaviour and axial wave numbers, the amplitude and phase angle vary, which can reduce the aerodynamic damping and create the flutter bite in certain regions of the operating map, usually close to the stall line [1–3].

Whereas intakes usually play no role in compressor and turbine flutter, acoustic propagation still does. In multi-row environments, acoustic coupling with neighbouring rows occurs due to reflections. Schoenenborn (2018) [4] performed a numerical

study on a quasi-3d research compressor using a harmonic balance solver and showed that by including the neighbouring rows the aerodynamic damping changed by up to 40%. Further investigations, focusing on the duct propagation in-between the blade rows can be found in Zhao et al. (2015) [5] and Yang et al. (2020) [6]. The authors emphasise the need to include neighbouring blade rows when cut-on modes are present in aerodynamic damping calculations. Gallardo et al. (2019) [7] investigated the effect of acoustic and nearly-convected (vorticity or entropy dominated) modes in a low-pressure turbine. A numerical radial mode analysis approach was used to decompose the pressure field into the acoustic and nearly convected modes. In this study all acoustic modes originating from the investigated structural modes are cut-off and the blade rows are spaced closely. The authors therefore found a relatively small decay of the acoustic amplitudes and relevant interactions due to the scattering in or from nearly convected modes.

Cut-on/cut-off conditions. Besides the acoustic propagation, also the acoustic conditions itself can influence the aerodynamic damping. In particular the cut-on/cut-off state of the acoustic waves which are excited by the blade vibrations was found to impact the aerodynamic damping. There are multiple publications on this topic; whereas all of them are based on numerical studies. A critical state was found by Vahdati & Cumpsty (2012) [8] for a transonic fan to be the condition where the acoustic mode is cut-on upstream and cut-off downstream of the blade. The cut-on/cut-off transition occurs over the blade mainly due to the increase in swirl velocity over the blade row. This leads to a drop in aerodynamic damping. Vahdati et al. (2015) [1] describe, that the acoustic waves are forced to travel upstream as they cannot propagate downstream due to the cut-off condition. The interaction of the acoustic wave with the leading edge of the blade “modifies the phase and amplitude” [1]. However, a detailed description on the physical mechanisms was not given. Regardless, Vahdati & Cumpsty (2016) [9] showed for the isolated fan stage that damping vs. frequency curves of different nodal diameters become very similar when normalising the frequency by the cut-off frequency. Here, the minimum occurred at the same normalised frequency for all nodal diameters.

Dong et al. (2022) [10] performed a numerical investigation, varying the vibration frequency of an isolated transonic fan blade row. They found flutter close to the stall line for two conditions: upstream cut-on/downstream cut-off and upstream cut-off/downstream cut-off. However, at a different operating point further away from the stall line the vibrations became stabilised when in the critical cut-on/cut-off area. Interestingly, the damping became similar for both operating points when the acoustic modes were cut-on upstream and downstream, highlighting the strong impact of the acoustic cut-on/cut-off state. Negative damping was driven mainly by the pressure side, where a sudden destabilisation happened when the downstream acoustic mode became cut-off. Very similar observations were made by

Yu et al. (2024) [11] for a transonic compressor. Goessling et al. (2024) [12] investigated the impact of both, the mode-shape and frequency on flutter in a transonic fan blade row. They aimed to test the plunge-to-twist incidence ratio, which combines the incidence change due to twist and plunge and, therefore, combines reduced frequency and twist-to-plunge ratio of the mode-shape. It was shown that the flutter behaviour was changed in upstream cut-on, downstream cut-off state, strongly deviating from the constant plunge-to-twist-incidence-ratio assumption. However, this led to a more stable blade. The trend was mainly driven by a suddenly more stable suction side of the blade when reaching the cut-on/cut-off state, while the pressure side’s damping was constantly diminishing with decreasing frequency. These observations partly deviate from the previous papers.

In summary, it was observed multiple times, that the aeroacoustics can highly impact the aerodynamic damping. However, until now there has not been a systematic clustering of these results, as the exact mechanisms (impact on shock, flow regimes up- and downstream of shock, pressure side) are still not understood. Additionally, all of these results rely on purely numerical investigations providing no experimental validation.

Background A series of aeroelastic investigations at TFD’s transonic 1½-stage axial compressor have been performed in the past. The compressor features a blisk and an acoustic excitation system, which can be used for damping measurements during operation. Maroldt et al. (2022) [13] performed experimental and numerical forced-response investigations at the compressor, showing, that at a low-speed resonance crossing the aerodynamic damping of the relevant mode changed by 22% when including inlet guide vanes (IGV) and the stator to the aerodynamic damping calculations. The results were supported by damping measurements based on acoustic excitation. Investigations with the same numerical setups were done by Maroldt & Seume (2025) [14], comparing the numerical results to extensive experimental results. The findings further validated the numerical setup and proves that accurate calculations of full damping curves are possible. However, the physical mechanisms have not been researched yet. The investigations were mainly performed for the first torsional mode family at a subsonic operating point at 44% design speed and for the first bending mode family at a transonic operating point at 90% design speed. Additional numerical and experimental data at different rotational speeds can be found in Maroldt (2023) [15]. In this work it was found that for 95% and 100% rotational speed a small, but systematic over-prediction of the experimental results by the CFD occurred for forward-travelling nodal diameters. Nevertheless, except for one nodal diameter at each damping curve, these deviations were still within the measurement uncertainty. It was concluded that these deviations occurred due to the high sensitivity of the shock to the operating conditions. However, later investigations showed no severe impact of small operating point changes.

Therefore, the objective of this paper is the investigation

FIGURE 1. 1/2-stage axial compressor configuration

of aerodynamic damping mechanisms in TFD's 1 1/2-stage axial compressor at transonic operating conditions to identify the cause of the deviations at forward-travelling nodal diameters and understand the damping mechanisms, focusing on the aeroacoustic propagation.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Test rig

The investigations were carried out at the transonic 1/2-stage axial compressor of the Institute of Turbomachinery and Fluid Dynamics (Leibniz University Hannover). The compressor was specifically designed for aeroelastic investigations [16], featuring a rotor blisk, a tip-timing system and an acoustic excitation system. The compressor configuration is shown in Fig. 1. It features 23 variable inlet guide vanes (IGV), a rotor with 24 blades and a stator with 27 rotatable vanes. In this paper the IGV is set to a fixed stagger angle of 0° and the stator to an angle of -10° . Additionally, upstream of the compressor stage 3 non-uniformly distributed struts (105° , 180° , 255°) are located. The hub-to-tip-ratio at the rotor is approximately 0.6 and the design speed is 17 100 rpm with a relative circumferential tip Mach number of 0.9. Further information regarding the test rig and the forced-response behaviour can be found in Maroldt et al. (2022) [13]. Investigations into the aerodynamic damping at 90% (mode family 1) and 44% rotational speed (mode family 3) can be found in Maroldt & Seume (2025) [14]. The paper shows that the numerical setup is able to predict the aerodynamic damping within the measurement uncertainty for all measured nodal diameters. Additionally, it was found that for nodal diameter (ND)-1, ND0, and ND1 blade vibrations couple with shaft vibrations which increases the system damping for these nodal diameters. It was shown that the increase in damping can be accurately predict by means of a finite element model of the whole rotor. However, as this effect is not of importance for the research topic at hand, these calculations will not be included in this paper.

In this paper a transonic operating point at design-speed (mechanical speed $n_{\text{mech}} = 17315$ rpm) is investigated. At this operating points no major flow separations are expected. Investigations will focus on the first mode family, which is the first flapwise mode. The eigenfrequencies f_0 at design speed lie be-

FIGURE 2. Mode shapes of mode family 1 at design speed

tween 745.4 Hz (nodal diameter 2, ND2) and 751.0 Hz (ND12). The mode shapes at design speed for ND2 and ND12 are shown in Fig. 2. The twist-to-plunge ratio [9] of the mode is 0.34 with a reduced frequency

$$k = \frac{2\pi f_0 c}{w} = 0.8 \quad (1)$$

with c being the chord length and w being the flow velocity in relative frame of reference, both at the tip.

Measurements of the damping were performed by means of acoustic excitation. The test rig is equipped with 8 speakers, located equidistantly around the circumference above the blade. At the chosen operating point a frequency sweep is performed around the eigenfrequency while maintaining constant rotational speed. The blade's response is measured and a single-degree-of-freedom fit was used to determine the damping. As the structural damping is negligible, this results corresponds to the aerodynamic damping (except for ND-1, ND0, ND1) [14]. To correct the impact of (small) mistuning a fundamental-mistuning-model based correction was applied [14]. Further information on the aeroacoustic excitation system can be in [17–19].

2.2 Numerical Setup

Numerical calculations were performed using the flow solver TRACE developed by the German Aerospace Center (DLR). The setup is the same as in [14], but the domain was extended upstream to include struts and inlet pipe, see Fig. 3. The mesh consists of 15.1 million nodes with a maximum y^+ -value of 3.5 and an average of 0.5. Although the implemented harmonic

FIGURE 3. Computational domain for the CFD calculations

balance method [20] features Giles 2d non-reflecting boundary conditions, which use a radial band-wise mode decomposition at inlet and outlet [21], acoustic reflections cannot be perfectly suppressed for 3-dimensional acoustic modes. Therefore, a sponge layer was placed at the inlet section of the pipe to damp acoustic reflections at the interfaces. The reflections at the stator outlet where found to be less significant, as a maximum radial mode order of 0 is cut-on here. An analysis of the reflection behaviour will be done in Sec. 4.2.

The k - ω turbulence model [22] with stagnation-point fix [23] and γ - Re_θ transition model [24] was used for modelling of the turbulence and transition. As inlet boundary conditions an axial flow with a constant total pressure and total temperature was defined. The total pressure was taken from the experimental data and was measured with an pitot tube at an axial position just downstream of the struts, but in the upper half of the compressor. The measurement was therefore undisturbed from the struts and approximately equal to the total pressure in the pipe. The total temperature was measured in the pipe close to the numerical inlet. At the outlet the measured mass flow rate was imposed.

Complex mode shapes were used, which were calculated using the same pre-stressed cyclic finite element model in ANSYS Mechanical as in [14]. The corresponding eigenfrequencies were validated in [14] using ping-tests and tip-timing measurements. Unsteady aerodynamic damping calculations were performed using the harmonic balance solver of TRACE and the mode shapes scaled to a maximum amplitude of 0.1 mm. Since a transonic operating point was investigated, the flow field was solved with 3 harmonics of the mode frequency in the rotor domain. In all other rows only the first harmonic was solved, since acoustic effects are usually considered linear. Besides the conserved quantities for mass, momentum, and energy, the turbulence transport variables k, ω were resolved with the corresponding harmonics as well. In order to stabilise the calculations, Lanczos-filtering was applied to k, ω [25]. To separate the influence of the individual vane rows, five numerical setups were calculated: {Struts IGV R1 S1}, {IGV R1 S1}, {IGV R1}, {R1 S1}, {R1}.

2.3 Radial mode analysis

The acoustic propagation in an annular duct can be described based on the linearised Navier-Stokes equations by the superposition of an infinite number of acoustic modes [26, 27]

$$p(x, r, \varphi) = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(A_{mn}^+ \cdot e^{-ik_{mn}^+ x} + A_{mn}^- \cdot e^{-ik_{mn}^- x} \right) f_{mn}(r) \cdot e^{-im\varphi} \quad (2)$$

with the circumferential mode order m and the radial mode order n . A positive sign of m and ND indicates a forward travelling wave. In this paper, unless stated otherwise, only radial mode order $n = 0$ is evaluated. The cut-off frequency of the acoustic modes is calculated based on the analytical solution, assuming a radially constant axial Mach-number and a solid-body swirl [28].

In order to decompose the acoustic field into upstream and downstream travelling modes, triple-plane pressure mode matching is used for radial mode analysis (RMA). The set of acoustic modes for the evaluation is calculated based on the radial distribution (circumferentially averaged) of axial and circumferential Mach-number, pressure, and density using a numerical modal analysis of the simplified linearized Navier-Stokes equations as described by Kousen [29] and Moinier & Giles [30]. A set of radial mode orders 0 to 3 are calculated and then fitted to the circumferentially decomposed unsteady pressure field. For every evaluation, three planes are used, where the flow-field of the first plane is used for the mode analysis (see Fig. 1). All radial eigenfunctions are scaled such that the modal amplitude describes the pressure at the shroud, as the shroud amplitude is considered as most relevant for the first bending mode investigated.

Due to the Doppler-shift, the blade eigenfrequencies are observed in the stationary frame of reference with a frequency shift

$$f_{\text{stat}} = |f_0 + \text{ND} \cdot n_{\text{mech}}| \quad (3)$$

and are shown in Fig. 4. Additionally, the cut-off frequencies up- and downstream of the rotor are shown for the corresponding circumferential mode order. Between IGV and rotor (upstream of the rotor) nodal diameters -1 to 12 are cut-on. It is noticeable too that with increasing nodal diameter the eigenfrequency in stationary frame of reference gets closer to the cut-off frequency. Due to the swirl downstream of the rotor between rotor and stator, only nodal diameters -1 to 3 are cut-on.

3 AERODYNAMICS

The numerically computed and measured speed line of the design speed (corrected rotational speed 17,100 rpm, mechanical speed 17,315 rpm) is shown in Fig 5. It can be seen that the two measured operating points at higher mass flow rates agree

FIGURE 4. Cut-off frequencies upstream and downstream of the rotor for the acoustic modes excited by nodal-diameter vibrations. The scatter-modes of the IGV between $m = -12$ and $m = 12$ are also shown as squares.

FIGURE 5. Total pressure ratio and mass flow rate at design speed

within the measurement uncertainty with the CFD. Small deviations due to the smaller slope arise towards the stall-line. In this study only the operating point highlighted with "OP" will be investigated. Therefore, the global performance parameters are accurately captured by the CFD.

Figure 6 shows the isentropic Mach number on the rotor blade at the operating point investigated. As it can be seen the compressor operates at a transonic operating point with a maximum Mach number of 1.5. On the suction side, a supersonic flow regime is visible which extends in the upper part of the blade to one quarter of the chord length, ending with a shock. No flow separations are present at the operating point investigated.

FIGURE 6. Isentropic Mach number distribution on the rotor blade

4 SETUP STUDY

Before performing deeper analysis, this section aims to investigate the sensitivities of the numerical setup in order to evaluate the significance of later archived results.

4.1 Linearity

In order to evaluate the impact of non-linearities in the flow field on the aerodynamic damping a sensitivity study was performed. As non-linearities are only expected in the rotor domain due to the shock, the computational domain was reduced to the isolated rotor domain. In order to evaluate the non-linearities the number of harmonics was varied from 3 (h3) to 1 (h1). Additionally, time domain (TD) calculations were run for ND4 and ND6 using a 6 and 4 passage model, respectively. The results are shown in Fig. 7. Deviations occur mainly at positive nodal diameters, where acoustic modes are cut-on upstream of the rotor. This suggests, that the small deviations are related to the propagation behaviour of the acoustic modes. However, the deviations lie below 3%, justifying the assumption of a linear behaviour. This allows further investigations using the superposition of different results. Moreover, it can be concluded that 1 harmonic would be sufficient for further investigations, but to avoid any unexpected changes when extending the computational domain, further investigations were performed using 3 harmonics.

4.2 2d non-reflecting boundary conditions

As mentioned before, the solver uses 2d non-reflecting boundary conditions (NRBC), but these are not necessary fully non-reflective for 3-dimensional acoustic modes. This is especially critical for the setup used in the previous Sec. 4.1 where

FIGURE 7. Damping curve of isolated rotor for different numerical setups

only the rotor is considered, as here inlet and outlet are close to the rotor domain. It is noted that the interfaces between blade rows are not reflective when the frequencies of both sides of the interface are coupled. Therefore, only inlet and outlet can create disturbing acoustic reflections in this work.

To evaluate the reflective behaviour, pressure-based reflection coefficients

$$R_p = \frac{|A_{p,refl}|}{|A_{p,out}|} \quad (4)$$

using pressure amplitudes of the outgoing waves $|A_{p,out}|$ (through the inlet and outlet) and the reflected waves $|A_{p,refl}|$ are calculated by means of radial mode analysis. As the axial space in the rotor domain is limited, the evaluation planes are spaced closely, which leads to high condition numbers for a few nodal diameters. This is especially relevant for modes close to the cut-off limit, as at the cut-off limit both up- and downstream modes possess the same axial wavenumber, which makes the decomposition of the acoustic field impossible. Based on experiences with the radial mode analysis, the limit for this investigation is set to 30.

The reflection behaviour of the inlet is shown in Fig. 8. Nodal diameters at which the condition number exceeds 30 are coloured gray and will not be considered in the discussion. It can be seen that the reflection coefficient increases with increasing absolute nodal diameter. It is assumed that this is due to the radial eigenfunctions deviating more from a plane wave. The reflection coefficient at the inlet reaches values up to 70%. However, as this acoustic mode is cut-off, the amplitude is very low and no large impact on the aerodynamic damping are expected. Investigations in Sec. 5 will show that pressure amplitudes of reflected waves become relevant at approximately 50 Pa in this case. At the inlet the reflection coefficient is below 30%, but the

FIGURE 8. Reflection behaviour of the inlet and outlet interface for the isolated rotor. Results for nodal diameter at which the condition number exceeds 30 are coloured gray.

outgoing modes reach amplitudes up to 505 Pa, leading to reflections of up to 141 Pa. As these modes are cut-on, this can have a significant impact on the aerodynamic damping.

In conclusion, for the following investigations it must be kept in mind that above ND7 reflections at the rotor inlet can significantly impact the aerodynamic damping for the isolated rotor simulations. For computational domains that include IGV or stator the reflections at both in- and outlet were found to be reduced, but as will be shown in Sec. 6 can still have a small impact on aerodynamic damping.

5 RESULTS WITHOUT STRUTS

5.1 Aerodynamic damping

In order to evaluate the impact of acoustic reflections at the neighbouring vane rows (IGV, S1), multiple setups have been calculated, excluding parts of the numerical setups. In this section the struts will not be considered to reduce the complexity of the analysis. The resulting damping curves are shown in

Fig 9 and compared with the experimental results. The isolated rotor results (R1) show the typical sine-shaped damping curve (also/clearer visible in Fig. 7), except at ND-2, where a small spike is visible. As this ND is (coming from larger nodal diameters) the first that is cut-off upstream and downstream, this spike is attributed to the known spikes at or close to cut-off frequencies. Further conclusions can be made from the results of the different setups. Interestingly, for IGV R1 S1, R1 S1, and the experiment this peak does not occur. This leads to the conclusion that the spike only occurs if the stator is not included and replaced by the outlet. Therefore, the peak could originate from reflections from the interface, but based on the study on the NRBC no conclusion can be made due to the high condition number. This type of spike in the damping curve is, however, well known in literature, see e.g. [10, 12].

The setup including IGV and stator (IGV R1 S1) deviates by up to 40% at ND6 from the R1 setup. Most of the deviations occur in the downstream cut-off, upstream cut-on area (above ND3). The results from IGV R1 S1 agree with the experiment at all nodal diameters, except ND6 and ND7. These are the nodal diameters where, as mentioned before, the differences between R1 and IGV R1 S1 are the largest, indicating a large impact of the acoustic interactions. Noticeable is also a drop in aerodynamic damping at ND11 and a subsequent increase at ND12, which is visible in the experimental data but can also be seen in the numerical results IGV R1 S1 and IGV R1. Therefore, the dip at ND11 is attributed to acoustic reflections occurring at the IGV.

To further separate the effects of the individual rows, the aerodynamic damping (logarithmic decrement Λ) is decomposed using the different numerical setups:

$$\Lambda_{\text{downstream}} = \Lambda_{\text{R1 S1}} - \Lambda_{\text{R1}} \quad (5)$$

$$\Lambda_{\text{upstream}} = \Lambda_{\text{IGV R1}} - \Lambda_{\text{R1}} \quad (6)$$

The results are shown in Fig. 10. KI As previously observed, the impact of the neighbouring rows is greatest when only upstream acoustic modes are cut on. The greatest impact is again observed at ND6, where the damping is increased by 2.7%pt. or more than 50%. However, the downstream effects, i.e., reflections at the stator, again decrease the damping by 0.7%pt. Also, it is noticeable, that both the up- and downstream effects show a continuous sine-like behaviour with varying amplitudes, leading to stabilisation or destabilisation, depending on the ND. This is also true for cut-off modes.

5.2 Acoustic behaviour

To further understand the reflection behaviour, the pressure amplitudes of the upstream and downstream acoustic waves are investigated in Fig 11. For the cut-off area (below ND-1) the acoustics behaves as expected. Low pressure amplitudes occur

both up- and downstream of the rotor, whereas the amplitudes of the reflected modes downstream of the rotor (at the stator) are larger as they are travelling upstream. In general, the amplitudes arriving at the rotor in the cut-off area are quite small, mostly below 25 Pa, compared to cut-on modes with amplitudes of up to 500 Pa.

For upstream outgoing waves at ND-1, a small peak in amplitude can be observed, as the cut-off ratio is close to unity (1.16), whereas for downstream outgoing waves at ND3 a slightly stronger peak can be observed, as the cut-off ratio is even closer to unity (1.04). It is noted that in contrast to the isolated rotor calculations, here an increased axial space due to the inclusion of the stator domain is available for the RMA, leading to a satisfactory condition number of 20.6 for ND3. The cut-off ratios for the other ND at which a transition from cut-on to cut-off occurs deviate more from unity and, therefore, do not lead to a peak in pressure.

As expected, large upstream outgoing pressure amplitudes are visible for only upstream cut-on modes (above ND3). This is because when the downstream modes become cut-off all acoustic energy is transported upstream as no downstream acoustic energy-transport is possible. Compared with the isolated rotor results (Fig. 8 top) the upstream outgoing amplitudes (dark red bars), which represent the acoustic modes excited by the blade vibrations, do not monotonously increase with increasing ND. It is assumed that this is a result of multiple reflections, i.e., acoustic modes reflected at the IGV and again at the rotor. Therefore, it can be concluded that the pressure amplitudes of the excited acoustic modes mainly depend on the cut-off ratio, with frequencies being closer to the cut-off frequency resulting in higher amplitudes. Another irregularity which has been observed at the damping curve (Fig. 9) is the dip in damping at ND11. However, looking at the proportions of the reflected waves in Fig. 11 (light red) it can be seen, that at ND12 a drop in reflected amplitude occurs. Consequently, the propagation or reflection behaviour at ND12 is somehow changed leading to a lower reflection coefficient at the IGV and therefore an increase in damping in Fig. 9. Contrary, the acoustic behaviour at ND11 follows the same trend as at lower nodal diameters, i.e., a high reflection at the IGV.

The reason for this phenomenon was traced back to the change of the cut-off state of a scatter mode at the IGV. As shown in Fig. 4 the scatter mode $m = 11 - 23 = -12$ for ND11 is cut-off, while the scatter mode $m = 12 - 23 = -11$ for ND12 is the only one to be cut-on upstream of the rotor. The resulting changes in propagation behaviour can be seen in Fig. 12. The figure shows the amplitudes $|A|$ of the acoustic modes travelling upstream and downstream. As seen before, for ND11 (Fig. 12 top) approximately 60% of the pressure amplitude coming from the rotor is reflected at the IGV. In addition, the same amount is scattered into circumferential mode order -12 . It is noted that no acoustic energy is produced here, as a balancing of sound power (not shown here) reveals that the upstream travelling wave

FIGURE 9. Damping curve of experiment and different setups, excluding the struts

FIGURE 10. Decomposition of aerodynamic damping (from IGV R1 S1) into rotor, upstream (IGV) and downstream (S1) effects without struts

$m = 11$ contains more energy than the reflected and scattered modes together. Upstream of the IGV a pressure amplitude of 110 Pa for $m = -12$ is visible (upstream travelling), which was transmitted through the IGV. However, since $m = -12$ is cut-off it will quickly decay and does not transport any acoustic energy. Figure 12 (bottom) shows the results for ND12. In this case the scatter mode $m = -11$ is cut-on upstream of the rotor and IGV. Therefore, acoustic energy can be transmitted through the IGV, leading to higher amplitudes upstream of the IGV and lower reflections downstream of the IGV. Consequently, the reflection coefficient at the IGV from ND11 to ND12 is decreased due to the

FIGURE 11. Pressure amplitudes of outgoing and reflected waves without struts (IGV R1 S1)

change from cut-off to cut-on of the scatter mode $m = -11$. This leads to a smaller impact of the acoustic reflections on the aerodynamic damping and, thus, less destabilisation.

In Fig. 11 it was shown that the generated sound pressure travelling upstream tends to increase with increasing nodal diameter. However, it was observed in Fig. 10 that the impact on aerodynamic damping does not increase, but is more sinusoidal-shaped. This is related to the phase angle of the reflected wave. The unsteady pressure has the most impact on the stability when it is 90° ahead of the deformation. Since the phase changes due

FIGURE 12. Acoustic propagation for ND11 (top) and ND12 (bottom), including lowest scatter mode at IGV without struts (IGV R1 S1)

to acoustic propagation within the blade row are not known, it is more convenient to investigate the reflected acoustic pressure from the IGV $A_{IGV \rightarrow R1}^+$ in 90° phase direction of the upstream trailing wave $\angle(A_{R1 \rightarrow IGV}^-)$ just upstream of the rotor leading edge. The resulting pressure projected in this direction is calculated as

$$A_{proj}^+ = \Im(A_{IGV \rightarrow R1}^+ \cdot e^{-i\angle A_{R1 \rightarrow IGV}^-}). \quad (7)$$

The same can be done downstream of the rotor. Figure 13 shows the resulting projected pressure resulting from the reflected waves. For the upstream reflections (at the IGV) it can be seen, that the pressure has a maximum at ND 7 and becomes negative at ND11, which represents a similar behaviour as observed in Fig. 10 for the impact of the IGV on the aerodynamic damping. Although the behaviour of the aerodynamic damping is not exactly represented by the projected pressure (see e.g. at

FIGURE 13. Projected pressure A_{proj} of the reflected wave in 90° direction of the outgoing wave (IGV R1 S1)

ND12: positive sign of the projected pressure compared to the destabilising impact in Fig 10), the results indicate, that the phase angle is responsible for the sine-shaped impact of the IGV. For the downstream impact the projected pressure shows a different impact than the calculated aerodynamic damping, which will be discussed below.

To better understand the local impact of the acoustic reflections at IGV and S1, ND6 will be investigated in more detail, as here the aerodynamic damping has greatly been impacted by acoustic effects. Fig. 14 shows the real part of the aerodynamic work on the suction and pressure side of the blade for different numerical setups at ND6. Here, negative aerodynamic work results in positive damping. For the isolated rotor calculation it is evident, that the shock introduces positive aerodynamic damping which results in destabilisation. However, the downstream area of the shock and the supersonic flow regime upstream of the shock introduce negative aerodynamic work, which leads to an overall positive logarithmic decrement of 4.25%. By including the IGV in the calculation (Fig. 14 middle), the aerodynamic damping almost doubles. This is caused by a more stabilising shock and supersonic flow regime. By including the downstream stator S1 (Fig. 14 right) the overall damping slightly decreases. On one hand the shock stabilises the vibration, on the other hand the downstream area shows slightly increased aerodynamic work over a large area, which overcomes the shock-impact. It is also noticeable that the supersonic flow regime is almost not affected by the downstream stator, as the acoustic waves cannot travel upstream in flow regimes with $Ma \geq 1$. Looking at the pressure side, only small differences are visible. In all cases the area close to the leading edge shows a stabilising effect, while the rest of the blade shows a destabilising effect. The transition line between negative and positive aerodynamic work moves further upstream when including both, IGV and stator. This leads to a larger area of positive aerodynamic work and, therefore, less aerodynamic

FIGURE 14. Real part of aerodynamic work on suction (SS) and pressure side (PS) for ND6 and different setups

damping.

The differences observed in Fig. 14 are only caused by aeroacoustic propagation and will be analysed further. For that purpose in Fig. 15, the unsteady suction-side blade pressure due to the acoustic interaction was calculated by taking the difference between the R1 S1 and R1 setups (reflections downstream, middle), as well as the IGVR1 and R1 setups (reflections upstream, bottom). Assuming linearity, these results represent a calculation where only the reflected acoustic mode is imposed at the inlet or outlet, respectively, without any blade vibration. Additionally, the isentropic Mach number is shown to identify the flow regimes. Looking at the reflections coming from downstream at S1 (Fig. 15 middle; from left to right side of the figure) a constant phase change for the pressure is visible between a relative chord length of 1 and 0.5, indicating a constant wave number. In this area the phase is always positive, having a destabilising effect. Approximately at the shock position the phase starts to drop and becomes negative, leading to a stabilisation in the shock area, where large pressure amplitudes of more than 400 Pa occur. Upstream of the shock the phase rises and becomes positive again, with slightly lower amplitudes than downstream of the shock. As the acoustic waves cannot propagate through the supersonic flow regime, the upstream pressure fluctuations must be caused by propagation through the subsonic part of the passage, close to the pressure side. It is noticeable, that the phase of the incident acoustic wave at the trailing edge (reflection downstream) devi-

FIGURE 15. Isentropic Mach number (top) and pressure amplitude and phase on the SS for the acoustic reflections occurring downstream (middle) and upstream (bottom) of the rotor at 98% channel height

ates by 180° from the phase at the shock. The phase difference between the shock and just downstream of the shock appears to be approximately 90° . Due to the large impact of the shock on the aerodynamic damping caused by the high pressure amplitude, this leads to the conclusion, that the stability is not necessarily most impacted if the acoustic wave is reflected with a 90° phase shift, as usually assumed.

Considering the reflections upstream at the IGVR (Fig 15 bottom), the pressure amplitudes are larger than for the reflections downstream, with a maximum amplitude of approximately 1,600 Pa. The phase angle remains negative over the whole suction side, leading to a stabilisation of the blade. Again, a phase difference of 90° appears between the shock and just downstream the shock, however, the phase angles stay negative, i.e., stabilising. As the downstream travelling waves usually have a higher wave length, the phase change downstream of the shock due to acoustic propagation is very small.

The results explain, why the projected pressure in Fig. 13 could approximate the upstream impact (phase angle constantly below 0), but not the downstream effect (phase angle varies locally). It appears, that a more complex model would be necessary for the downstream reflections, as the shock leads to a phase jump, which counteracts the rest of the blade's influence. It is expected that the impact of the acoustic waves can be described in simpler terms if no shock is present.

FIGURE 16. Damping curve of experiment and different setups, including the struts

6 RESULTS WITH STRUTS

The previous results have shown that the upstream part of the compressor plays a major role in aerodynamic damping. Therefore, the numerical setup was extended to include the struts and the inlet pipe. In this way, acoustic reflections at the struts and the impedance jump at the bulb are included in the flutter calculations. The resulting damping curve is shown in Fig. 16. Visible differences between the setup without struts (IGV R1 S1) and with struts (Struts IGV R1 S1) are present above ND4 with up to 7%. This is in line with the previous observations as the amplitudes of the excited upstream-travelling acoustic modes increase with increasing nodal diameters. By including the struts in the setup, the numerical results match the experimental results within the measurement uncertainty for all nodal diameters, in particular ND6 and ND7, which are not predicted correctly with the IGV R1 S1 setup.

To find the reasons for the changes due to the inclusion of the struts in the numerical setup, Fig. 17 displays the amplitudes of the acoustic modes for the setups IGV R1 S1 (top) and Struts IGV R1 S1 (bottom). Both setups show very similar amplitudes downstream of the rotor with deviations below 3 Pa. Upstream of the rotor, however, larger differences occur. In the calculation with the struts (Struts IGV R1 S1) only 18 Pa of the 220 Pa of the acoustic mode travelling upstream between struts and IGV are reflected towards IGV, whereas in the calculation without the struts (IGV R1 S1) 53 Pa are reflected. This is a direct result of the reflection of the outgoing acoustic wave at the inlet. In consequence, due to the reflection at the inlet, the pressure amplitude of the acoustic mode reaching the rotor is increased by 20 Pa in the IGV R1 S1 setup, which ultimately is responsible for the decrease in damping. The struts itself seem to only cause

FIGURE 17. Pressure amplitudes for ND6 and radial mode order $n = 0, 1, 2$ for the setup without struts (IGV R1 S1, top) and with struts (Struts IGV R1 S1, bottom)

small reflections. Downstream of the struts only small pressure amplitudes of downstream travelling modes are visible, which are already visible upstream of the struts. Therefore, the main reason here seems to be the reflection at the impedance jump at the bulb.

7 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

In this work the impact of aeroacoustic propagation on aerodynamic damping was investigated. The results were compared with experimental data to evaluate the prediction quality. The key findings can be summarised as follows:

1. Blade vibrations excite acoustic modes, which can be reflected at (neighbouring) blade/vane rows and struts.
2. Reflected cut-off modes can still impact the aerodynamic damping.
3. The pressure amplitude of the acoustic modes excited by blade vibrations increases with increasing cut-off ratios.
4. The acoustic reflections at neighbouring rows are higher, if no scatter-modes are cut-on, potentially having a larger impact on the aerodynamic damping.
5. High pressure amplitudes of reflected waves can still cause a small impact on aerodynamic damping, if the phase angle on the blade is close to 0° or 180° .
6. The shock leads, for acoustic waves, propagating through the passage, to a phase-jump in the unsteady blade-pressure distribution. The resulting phase variations over the chord length make it more difficult to describe the acoustic impact on aerodynamic damping.
7. As acoustic cut-on modes preserve the energy during propagation, acoustic reflections can occur at any parts of the compressor (such as struts), impacting the aerodynamic damping.
8. At the investigated operating point, the inclusion of the struts in the computational domain eliminated reflections occurring at the prior inlet, which improved the prediction of the aerodynamic damping, meaning that the reflections at the boundary conditions are slightly larger in magnitude than the physical reflections at the struts. An impact on aerodynamic damping of up to 7% was observed, which eliminated remaining deviations larger than the measurement uncertainties between experiment and numerical simulation.

The results show that for accurate flutter predictions (at least) the neighbouring blade rows need to be included for cut-on and close-to-cut-on modes, which, in this case, led to changes of up to 50%. Additionally, care must be taken when handling the numerical boundary conditions. As most solvers feature no or only 2d non-reflecting boundary conditions, sponge layers should be used at both in- and outlet.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors gratefully acknowledge the funding of part of the present work through CRC 871 “Regeneration of Complex Capital Goods”, funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) – SFB 871/3 – 119193472. Moreover, the authors would like to thank Mona Amer and Igor Mamryuk for their support during the measure-

ments. In addition, the authors would like to acknowledge the substantial contribution of the DLR Institute of Propulsion Technology and MTU Aero Engines AG by providing TRACE.

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